

Electron Spin-Lattice Relaxation of Toluene and *p*-Xylene Anions[†]

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Electron spin-lattice relaxation times (T_{1e}) of toluene and *p*-xylene anions have been determined by the pulsed saturation recovery technique. Toluene anion exhibits short and nearly temperature independent T_{1e} ($1.8 \pm 0.4 \mu\text{s}$) in the temperature range studied (188 to 205 K). This is in agreement with the fact that toluene anion has a close lying excited orbital state at about 500 cm^{-1} and the temperature behaviour follows closely that observed earlier for T_{1e} of benzene anion (orbitally degenerate system) in CW saturation studies. *p*-Xylene anion exhibits larger T_{1e} 's ($9.5 \mu\text{s}$ at 205 K) and is a linear function of (η/T) with zero intercept. *p*-Xylene anion has been estimated to have its first electronic excited state at 1500 cm^{-1} . It is proposed that Orbach type mechanisms arising from a closely lying excited electronic level are dominant for spin-lattice relaxation in toluene anion. In *p*-xylene anion, however, spin rotation interaction is believed to play the dominant role with Orbach type processes being insignificant since $1500 \text{ cm}^{-1} \gg kT$.

THE alkyl substituted benzene anion radicals are known to have low lying excited orbital states and have been the subject of intense studies by electron spin resonance (esr) for several years. One of the most important consequences of the orbital degeneracy is the short electron spin-lattice relaxation time¹⁻³, T_{1e} , and large esr linewidth⁷⁻⁹ (short electron spin-spin relaxation time, T_{2e}) for benzene anion radical. It is expected that vibronic interaction would lift this degeneracy even in benzene anion. Different alkyl substitutions will lift the degeneracy to different extents. The magnitude of the splitting has been estimated theoretically¹⁰ and experimentally^{11,12}.

Measurements of T_{1e} of benzene and substituted benzene anions utilising the continuous-wave (CW) saturation technique have been made^{1,2,5,6}. It is well known that such estimates of T_{1e} by CW saturation technique suffer from unreliability in view of the difficulty in measuring true linewidths and the amplitude of the microwave magnetic field, H_1 . Greater would be the ambiguity when one faces inhomogeneous broadening which is bound to occur in the case of hydrocarbon anions due to their interaction with counter ions. A fair amount of effort has been made to estimate such effects and apply corrections to T_{1e} 's measured by the CW saturation technique⁸. However, it has been our experience that T_{1e} 's measured in this way have not always been reliable¹³. Such examples will be pointed out even in this paper.

The most direct way of measuring T_{1e} is the pulsed saturation recovery technique which has been applied for several years to free radicals in

solution in our laboratory and a few other laboratories¹⁴⁻¹⁸. With the recent availability in our laboratory of a computer controlled time domain pulsed esr spectrometer capable of extensive signal averaging¹⁹, we have been able to extend our sensitivity to measure T_{1e} 's of radicals at very low concentrations, $\sim 5 \times 10^{-6} M$, for a single esr line of width about 0.5 G. Alkyl substituted benzene anions are known to be obtained by alkali metal reduction process only in these concentration ranges (10^{-4} to $10^{-6} M$) and hence, our spectrometer is eminently suitable for studying such systems.

The mechanism of spin-lattice relaxation of free radicals in solutions have been established fairly well except in those cases where orbital degeneracy exists²⁰. In such cases, it is believed²¹ that an Orbach type of mechanism is dominant when the splitting between the two electronic states is less than $6 kT$, where k is the Boltzmann constant. However, there is controversy regarding the exact nature of the mechanism and many models have been proposed²¹⁻²⁵. It is believed that measurements of T_{1e} 's of several alkyl substituted benzene anions in different solvents over different ranges of temperature would throw light on the mechanisms based on the Orbach model. We present here a preliminary report on our measurements of T_{1e} 's, by the pulsed saturation recovery technique, of toluene and *p*-xylene anions in dimethoxyethane (DME) solution.

Experimental

Pulsed esr spectrometer: The pulsed esr spectrometer is a home-built homodyne X-band spectro-

[†] Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

A Part of the article was Presented at the National Conference on Spectroscopy and Theoretical Chemistry held at Calcutta, December 5-7, 1985.

meter¹⁹ similar to the one described by Fessenden and coworkers¹⁸. There is a facility to change independently the microwave pump power and the 'observe' power and to change the phase of the pump power by 180° between alternate experiments in order to separate free induction decay signal and the saturation recovery signal from the observed M_y component of the magnetisation as has been suggested by Percival and Hyde¹⁸. The magnetic field and microwave frequency interlock ensures that the resonance condition for any desired position of the esr line is maintained for any length of time, allowing extensive signal averaging.

The temperature of the sample was varied by flowing precooled nitrogen gas through a quartz Dewar inserted into the microwave cavity. The temperature of the nitrogen gas was controlled using a Varian 4540 temperature control accessory. The sample temperature was monitored with a POWERTEK digital thermometer using a chromel-alumel thermocouple. The temperature was maintained constant to ± 1 K.

Chemicals: Toluene and *p*-xylene (S.M. and Fluka, respectively) were used without further purification. The DME (Aldrich) solvent was distilled from sodium and dehydrated by lithium aluminium hydride. It was then distilled under vacuum into a storage vessel containing sodium mirror and anthracene. The formation of deep green anthracene dianion showed that the solvent was free from oxygen or any other paramagnetic impurity.

Sample preparation: The anion radicals were prepared by the well known alkali metal reduction process using potassium under high vacuum. At temperatures below 230 K, both the radicals gave blue colour indicating their presence. The concentration of the radicals were estimated by comparison with a standard sample of a nitroxide as described elsewhere²⁰.

Measurements of saturation recovery signal: The measurement of the saturation recovery signal involved a cycle of 4 experiments. In order to suppress the transients arising from the microwave pulses, a signal, obtained when the magnetic field was off resonance, was subtracted from the signal when it was at resonance. It was repeated for the other phase of the pump power. The whole cycle was repeated a desired number of times to improve the signal to noise ratio so that weak signals could be studied.

Results

In a typical experiment, the observed saturation recovery signal is shown in Fig. 1(a) and 1(b) for toluene and *p*-xylene anions, respectively. The electron spin-lattice relaxation times are estimated by the least-square fit of the curves to a single exponential. We did not find any discernible free induction decay signal from either of the systems,

Fig. 1. Saturation recovery curves for (a) toluene anion and (b) *p*-xylene anion in DME at 200 K and 195 K, respectively. The noisy traces are the averaged signal after R experiments and the smooth curves are fits to single exponentials with denoted T_{1e} 's.

indicating very short effective spin-spin relaxation times for both cases.

Toluene anion: Fig. 2 shows the second derivative esr spectrum of toluene anion in DME at 196 K. The measurements of T_{1e} were carried out not at the central line but at the line indicated by the arrow since at the centre there are two closely spaced lines. For off-resonance, the field was placed at the position marked 'A' in the Fig. The range of temperature variation has been limited because of

Fig. 2. Second derivative esr spectrum of toluene anion at 196 K. The T_{1e} 's were measured by observing the saturation recovery for the line marked with the arrow.

the considerable increase in linewidths at temperatures higher than 210 K. The large number of hyperfine lines also places a limit on the sensitivity for toluene anion. However, it is noted that in the temperature range of measurement, viz. 185 to 210 K, there is no discernible temperature dependence of T_{1e} within experimental error (Fig. 3).

It was found that at 'observe' power greater than even 0.2 mW, the saturation recovery traces had non-exponential shapes as predicted by the Bloch equations¹⁸. It was, therefore, necessary to observe the saturation recovery at 'observe' powers between 0.1 and 0.02 mW. At these power levels, the traces were nearly exponential, but with poor signal to noise ratio even after taking averages of 20 000 experiments. The T_{1e} determined under these conditions were nearly the same for the two. In

Fig. 3. Plot of T_{1e} 's of *p*-xylene and toluene anions as a function of η/T . The concentrations of the radicals are given in Fig. 1. η values are taken from Ref. 28.

view of the above difficulties, the values of T_{1e} reported here are accurate to about 20%.

p-Xylene anion: Since *p*-xylene anion has a smaller number of hyperfine lines, the signal to noise ratio for its esr signal is better than that of toluene anion for similar radical concentrations. The relaxation of the central line was studied and for off-resonance the field was placed between it and the neighbouring line.

In contrast to toluene anion, the exponential nature of the saturation recovery signal was seen to be valid upto 2.0 mW of 'observe' power. Since T_{1e} determined in this way is dependent upon the amplitude of the 'observe' microwave power, the true T_{1e} was determined from the limiting value at zero observing power, from a $1/T_{1e}$ vs ('observe' power) plot²⁷. A typical plot of such measurements is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Plot of $1/T_{1e}$ vs 'observe' microwave power for *p*-xylene anion at 205 K.

In the temperature ranging from 185 to 225 K, the T_{1e} for *p*-xylene anion changes from 9.5 to 5.0 μ s with an accuracy of better than 10%.

Discussion

From analysis of proton hyperfine splitting constants^{11,12} and theoretical studies¹⁰, it has been estimated that the separation between the ground state and the lowest excited electronic state is about 500 cm^{-1} in toluene anion and about 1500 cm^{-1} in *p*-xylene anion. Thus, one would expect Orbach type of mechanisms to be more important for relaxations in toluene anion. Since 1500 cm^{-1} is greater than $6kT$ ($\sim 834 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 200 K), it is expected that the major relaxation mechanisms for *p*-xylene anion would be processes other than the Orbach mechanisms.

If the equation (74) of Kivelson^{22(b)} is right we should expect for toluene anion, T_{1e} to be comparable to that calculated by him for benzene anion assuming an energy separation (δ) of 500 cm^{-1} . With parameters of Table 1 in his paper for benzene anion, the equation predicts about 1 μ s for T_{1e} with $\delta=500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 200 K. However, the temperature dependence of τ_e in his equation is left vague. From the analysis of the data of Jones and coworkers^{1,2} on benzene anion, it is noted that no clear temperature dependence is established within experimental errors. For the temperature range in their experiments (154 to 200 K) T_{1e} should have increased by a factor of 3 at lower temperatures if τ_e is assumed to be temperature independent and $\delta=500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the Kivelson equation. This temperature dependence will decrease drastically if one assumes a smaller δ (e.g. the ratio of T_{1e} 's is only 1.23 for $\delta=100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). For the temperature range of our measurements for toluene anion (188 to 205 K) assuming τ_e to be nearly temperature independent, the T_{1e} 's should vary in the ratio of 1.4 for $\delta=500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and our data (Fig. 3) exhibits no temperature dependence within the limits of experimental error. This behaviour is similar to that of benzene anion, a clear case of nearly orbitally degenerate system^{1,2}. From all these evidences we infer that as in benzene anion, Orbach mechanisms arising from a closely lying excited electronic level are the major contribution to spin-lattice relaxation in toluene anion. Without more refined data it would not be possible to comment meaningfully on the validity of Kivelson mechanism²² or of other mechanisms based on Orbach type processes^{21,25}.

Fig. 3 depicts the dependence of T_{1e} on η/T for *p*-xylene anion also. The linear relationship is well demonstrated and the intercept is zero. Such a behaviour is followed in cases where spin-rotation interaction is dominant^{1,2,15}. This behaviour is in great contrast to what is observed in toluene anion. The contribution from modulation of *g*-anisotropy and hyperfine anisotropy is expected to be very small since no marked line width variation among hyperfine components is observed. Further, in both toluene and *p*-xylene anions, exchange interactions are expected to be insignificant at these concentrations. However, a more careful investigation is yet to be carried out.

Freed and coworkers⁶ have determined T_{1e} of *p*-xylene anion to be 1.94 μ s at 203 K by CW saturation technique. This is to be compared with our value of $9.5 \pm 0.5 \mu$ s at 205 K. The most probable error in the earlier measurement must have been the unreliability in determining T_2 in the presence of unresolved hyperfine splitting.

The study of electron spin-lattice relaxation of radicals in solution with close lying excited electronic states by the saturation recovery technique has demonstrated the effect of Orbach mechanisms on T_{1e} 's. It is noted that these effects dominate when the energy separation is less than 6 kT and for separation of the order of 400 cm^{-1} , T_{1e} 's are nearly temperature independent. A systematic study of several alkyl substituted anions with different energy separations is expected to throw light on the details of the relaxation mechanisms operating in nearly degenerate systems.

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